

Supplement B

Evaluated articles

1. De Santis O, Audran R, Pothin E, et al. Safety and immunogenicity of a chimpanzee adenovirus-vectored Ebola vaccine in healthy adults: a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled, dose-finding, phase 1/2a study. *Lancet Infect Dis.* 2016;16(3):311-20.
2. Haller MJ, Atkinson MA, Wasserfall CH, et al. Mobilization without immune depletion fails to restore immunological tolerance or preserve beta cell function in recent onset type 1 diabetes. *Clin Exp Immunol.* 2016;183(3):350-7.
3. Fischer K, Bahlo J, Fink AM, et al. Long-term remissions after FCR chemoimmunotherapy in previously untreated patients with CLL: updated results of the CLL8 trial. *Blood.* 2016;127(2):208-15.
4. Beachler DC, Kreimer AR, Schiffman M, et al. Multisite HPV16/18 Vaccine Efficacy Against Cervical, Anal, and Oral HPV Infection. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 2015;108(1):djv302.
5. Rapaport MH, Nierenberg AA, Schettler PJ, et al. Inflammation as a predictive biomarker for response to omega-3 fatty acids in major depressive disorder: a proof-of-concept study. *Mol Psychiatry.* 2016;21(1):71-9.
6. Landin H, Mörk MJ, Larsson M, Waller KP. Vaccination against *Staphylococcus aureus* mastitis in two Swedish dairy herds. *Acta Vet Scand.* 2015;57:81.

7. Raatz SK, Johnson LK, Picklo MJ. Consumption of Honey, Sucrose, and High-Fructose Corn Syrup Produces Similar Metabolic Effects in Glucose-Tolerant and -Intolerant Individuals. *J Nutr.* 2015;145(10):2265-72.
8. Genovese MC, Hsia E, Belkowski SM, et al. Results from a Phase IIA Parallel Group Study of JNJ-40346527, an Oral CSF-1R Inhibitor, in Patients with Active Rheumatoid Arthritis despite Disease-modifying Antirheumatic Drug Therapy. *J Rheumatol.* 2015;42(10):1752-60.
9. Ma JK, Drossard J, Lewis D, et al. Regulatory approval and a first-in-human phase I clinical trial of a monoclonal antibody produced in transgenic tobacco plants. *Plant Biotechnol J.* 2015;13(8):1106-20.
10. Mily A, Rekha RS, Kamal SM, et al. Significant Effects of Oral Phenylbutyrate and Vitamin D3 Adjunctive Therapy in Pulmonary Tuberculosis: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *PLoS One.* 2015;10(9):e0138340.
11. Bhatia A, Sharma RK, Tewari S, Narula SC. A randomized clinical trial of salivary substitute as an adjunct to scaling and root planing for management of periodontal inflammation in mouth breathing patients. *J Oral Sci.* 2015;57(3):241-7.
12. Andres C, Plana M, Guardo AC, et al. HIV-1 Reservoir Dynamics after Vaccination and Antiretroviral Therapy Interruption Are Associated with Dendritic Cell Vaccine-Induced T Cell Responses. *J Virol.* 2015;89(18):9189-99.
13. Debrah AY, Specht S, Klarmann-Schulz U, et al. Doxycycline Leads to Sterility and Enhanced Killing of Female *Onchocerca volvulus* Worms in an Area With Persistent

Microfilaridermia After Repeated Ivermectin Treatment: A Randomized, Placebo-Controlled, Double-Blind Trial. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2015;61(4):517-26.

14. Hunter DJ, Beavers DP, Eckstein F, et al. The Intensive Diet and Exercise for Arthritis (IDEA) trial: 18-month radiographic and MRI outcomes. *Osteoarthritis Cartilage.* 2015;23(7):1090-8.

15. Nilsson C, Hejdeman B, Godoy-Ramirez K, et al. HIV-DNA Given with or without Intradermal Electroporation Is Safe and Highly Immunogenic in Healthy Swedish HIV-1 DNA/MVA Vaccinees: A Phase I Randomized Trial. *PLoS One.* 2015;10(6):e0131748.

16. Lo MM, Mbao V, Sierra P, et al. Safety and immunogenicity of Onderstepoort Biological Products' Rift Valley fever Clone 13 vaccine in sheep and goats under field conditions in Senegal. *Onderstepoort J Vet Res.* 2015;82(1):857.

17. Fuchs CS, Azevedo S, Okusaka T, et al. A phase 3 randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial of ganitumab or placebo in combination with gemcitabine as first-line therapy for metastatic adenocarcinoma of the pancreas: the GAMMA trial. *Ann Oncol.* 2015;26(5):921-7.

18. Joachim A, Nilsson C, Aboud S, et al. Potent functional antibody responses elicited by HIV-I DNA priming and boosting with heterologous HIV-1 recombinant MVA in healthy Tanzanian adults. *PLoS One.* 2015;10(4):e0118486.

19. Wheatley CM, Baker SE, Morgan MA, et al. Effects of exercise intensity compared to albuterol in individuals with cystic fibrosis. *Respir Med.* 2015;109(4):463-74.

20. Treven P, Mrak V, Bogovič Matijašić B, Horvat S, Rogelj I. Administration of probiotics *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG and *Lactobacillus gasseri* K7 during pregnancy and lactation changes mouse mesenteric lymph nodes and mammary gland microbiota. *J Dairy Sci.* 2015;98(4):2114-28.